

Biotherapeutic Diterpene Glucosides from *Tinospora* Species

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Clerodane furano diterpene glucosides isolated and characterised from various *Tinospora* species are reviewed. Their biological evaluation and ^{13}C nmr data are also discussed.

Tinospora genus belonging to family Menispermaceae consists of deciduous woody climber, distributed in tropics of Asia, Africa and Australia. There are about six species of *Tinospora* of which only first three occurs in the country^{1,2}: *Tinospora cordifolia* Miers., *T. malabarica* Miers., *T. crispa* Miers. (Syn. : *T. tuberculata* Beume, *T. rumphii* Miers.), *T. capillipes* Gagnep., *T. dentata* Diels. and *T. glabra* Merrill.

Considerable work on the chemical constituents of different *Tinospora* species have been undertaken and over sixty compounds isolated and fully identified. These may be broadly classified under the following heads: (i) clerodane furano diterpenes³⁻¹⁷, (ii) clerodane furanoditerpene glucosides¹²⁻¹⁹, (iii) steroids²⁰, (iv) flavonoids^{21,22}, (v) lignans^{23,24} and (vi) alkaloids^{25,26}.

Tinospora contains most important group of diterpene derivatives known as clerodane furano diterpene which are responsible for bitterness^{16,17}. However, their glucosides are somewhat less bitter. Each of these compounds contains one D-glucose molecule attached via a β -glucoside linkage.

The aqueous extract of these plants are widely used in traditional system of medicine for the treatment of jaundice, rheumatism, urinary diseases, intermittent fever, eye^{1,2} and liver²⁷ ailments. There is no report on the pharmacological investigation on clerodane furano diterpene glucosides of these species. We herein present a brief review on clerodane furano diterpene glucosides

of *Tinospora* species. Till this date about twelve such compounds have been characterised. These are borapetoside A¹² (1), B¹³ (2), C (3), D (4), E (5), F (6) and G¹⁴ (7) from stem of *T. tuberculata*, tinocrisposide¹⁵ (8) from *T. crispa* stem, tinoside (9) from *T. capillipes*¹⁷ rhizome, tinosporaside 10 and 11 from *T. cordifolia*^{18,19}

stem bark and further more we have recently isolated cordioside (**12**) and stereoisomer clerodane furanoditerpene glucosides (**11**) from *T. cordifolia* stem.

The clerodane furano diterpene glucosides are composed of aglycon (furanoditerpene) and sugar unit, which are recovered after hydrolysis and investigated separately. Normally acid hydrolysis is used, since clerodanes contain acid labile groups, enzymatic hydrolysis is preferred for specific cleavage of glucoside linkage.

The sugar moiety is determined by direct comparison, while ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectroscopy are used for the determination of anomeric mode of sugar linkage. The determination of structure of clerodane furano diterpene glucosides by spectroscopic method has the advantage of examining the intact molecule. The complete structure deter-

mination is possible by high field FT-NMR spectroscopy alone. The newer technique of mass spectroscopy particularly FD-MS and FAB-MS are of immense help in the determination of mass spectrum of clerodane furano diterpene glucoside with sugar units attached. The following examples illustrate the legance of these techniques in the structure elucidation of clerodane furano diterpene glucosides.

The structure of clerodane furano diterpene glucoside has been determined using ^1H nmr spectroscopy. Although the ^1H nmr spectra of underivatized clerodane furano diterpene glucoside exhibit considerable line-broadening, the spectra of corresponding peracetates are well-resolved. A high field ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectrum (Tables 1 and 2) of the tinosporoside tetraacetate showed that the glucose proton resonance splits into zones between δ 4.94, 5.18 and 5.04 assigned to CHOAc, the other between δ 4.14 and 4.11 assigned to CH_2OAc and anomeric proton appeared at δ 4.65.

Olefinic resonances in the ^1H nmr spectrum at δ 6.41, 7.43 and 7.52 were typical for a 3-substituted furan ring and an isolated ABX system at δ 5.47, 1.82 and 2.25 could be assigned to H-12 and H-11 protons with H-12 being axial. Angular methyl groups were observed as singlets at δ 1.18 and 0.80. Two further olefinic protons resonated at δ 5.99 and 6.70 typical of the α - and β -protons of an α,β -unsaturated ketone. The β -proton showed an additional coupling to a proton resonating at δ 4.22, which could be assigned to the carbinolic position of glucose attachment. A sharp singlet at δ 2.17 and broad singlet at δ 2.30 are assigned to H-7 and H-8 respectively.

The stereochemistry of compound **10** tetraacetate was further explored by Waterman *et al.*¹⁸ through a series of NOE experiments. Their key observations were (i) a strong interaction between H-12 and H-10, (ii) H-8 and H-10 are on opposite faces, (iii) irradiation of Me-20 caused strong enhancement of H-11_{ax}, H-8, H-7_{ax} and

TABLE 1-¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF DITERPENE GLUCOSIDES

C	1*	2*	10-OAc ₄ **	11-OAc ₄ **
1				1.55 (2H, m)
2			5.99 (1H, d, 10.3)	1.63 (1H, m)
3	4.04	6.34	6.70 (1H, ddd, 10.3, 4.9, 1.3)	1.75 (1H, m)
4			4.22 (1H, d, 4.9)	-
6a	5.02		2.25 (1H, ddd, 14.3, 4.0, 4.0)	4.58 (1H, brs)
6b			1.02 (1H, ddd 14.3, 14.0, 3.8)	-
7a			2.19 (1H, m)	2.85 (1H, brd, 15.19)
7b			1.63 (1H, dddd, 14.3, 14.1, 8.3, 1.5)	2.16 (1H, m)
8	2.78		2.30 (1H, brs)	2.44 (1H, m)
10			2.17 (1H, s)	2.38 (1H, m)
11a			2.25 (1H, dd, 15.0, 3.6)	2.27 (1H, dd, 14.68, 3.26)
11b			1.82 (1H, dd, 15.0, 12.2)	2.44 (1H, m)
12	5.90	5.49	5.47 (1H, dd, 12.2, 3.6)	5.45 (1H, dd, 12.6, 2.74)
14	6.55	6.56	6.41 (1H, dd, 1.4, 0.9)	6.45 (1H, brs)
15	7.51	7.65	7.43 (1H, t, 1.4)	7.43 (1H, brs)
16	7.64	7.71	7.52 (1H, t, 0.9)	7.48 (1H, brs)
Me	1.23, 1.12	1.45, 0.85	1.18, 0.80	1.03
CO ₂ Me		3.69 (3H, s)		3.74 (3H, s)
Sugar part				
1'	4.33	4.27	4.65 (1H, d, 7.7)	4.60 (1H, d, 7.99)
2'			4.94 (1H, dd, 9.5, 7.8)	5.14 (1H, t, 9.50)
3'			5.18 (1H, t, 9.4)	4.90 (1H, t, 8.77)
4'			5.04 (1H, t, 9.6)	5.07 (1H, t, 9.69)
5'			3.65 (1H, ddd, 10.0, 4.6, 2.9)	3.66 (1H, m)
6'a			4.14 (1H, dd, 12.4, 4.8)	4.28 (1H, dd, 12.24, 4.34)
6'b			4.11 (1H, dd, 12.4, 2.8)	4.14 (1H, brd, 12.20)
OCOMe			2.01 (3H, s)	2.10 (3H, s)
			1.99 (3H, s)	2.02 (6H, s)
			1.97 (3H, s)	2.00 (3H, s)
			1.97 (3H, s)	

*Measured in DMSO-d₆; **Measured in CDCl₃, coupling constant (*J*) in Hz.

H-4 which suggests *cis*-B/C ring junction and places H-4 on the same face as Me-20 and (iv) irradiation of Me-19 causes a strong enhancement of H-10 confirming that the A/B ring junction is *cis*.

The furano diterpene glucoside (**11**) reported without C-19 angular methyl group by Sabata *et al.*¹⁹ is interesting from biogenetic angle. The structure was established with the help of high resolution ¹H nmr spectra of parent and its tetraacetate. We have also isolated a similar compound with opposite specific rotation indicating it to be the stereoisomer of **11**.

The technique of fast atom bombardment (FAB)

mass spectrometry has become one of the most powerful tools in structural investigation of polar molecules. This technique was successfully used for determination of the molecular weight of *Tinospora* glucosides, the appearance of (*M* + *K*)⁺ and (*M* + *Na*)⁺ ion peaks helped in finding out the molecular weight for both compounds (**11**) and cordioside (**12**). The FAB mass spectra showed fragmentations at *m/z* 81, 94 and 95²⁸ accounting for loss of furan moiety, i.e. cleavage of δ-lactone ring along with C-9/C-11-C-12 bonds indicating furan ring occupying C-12 position with δ-lactone in its vicinity.

No pharmacological investigations have been

TABLE 2 ^{13}C NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF DITERPENE GLUCOSIDES

C	1*	2*	10-OAc ₄ **	11-OAc ₄ **
1	17.4	28.0	201.8	17.45
2	24.6	62.2	129.4	21.98
3	75.6	140.2	141.8	26.25
4	79.5	137.4	72.0	143.47
5	45.2	40.9	43.3	128.55
6	69.8	79.0	29.2	72.85
7	27.2	26.4	18.9	27.84
8	46.3	49.2	48.7	49.28
9	34.3	36.5	35.5	38.19
10	46.1	40.5	48.5	39.13
11	42.9	44.0	40.6	39.65
12	69.4	69.9	69.8	71.28
13	124.2	124.5	124.6	124.78
14	108.7	109.2	108.0	108.23
15	140.3	140.2	144.7	139.38
16	143.5	143.7	139.5	144.99
17	172.6	174.6	171.0	171.13
18	177.6	167.5	-	169.12
19	32.6	28.4	31.1	23.38
20	17.9	22.8	25.7	-
CO ₂ Me		51.6		
1'	102.4	104.6	100.3	98.99
2'	74.1	73.9	71.4	70.36
3'	76.7	77.4	72.2	72.66
4'	73.1	69.4	68.0	68.12
5'	75.8	76.6	72.0	71.29
6'	60.7	61.0	61.6	61.77
OCOMe			170.2/20.5	170.31/20.30
			170.0/20.4	169.94/20.30
			169.9/20.3	168.73/20.30
			168.7/20.3	167.77/20.33

*Measured in DMSO-d₆; **Measured in CDCl₃.

reported on these glucosides. We have screened tinosporaside (10), 11 and cordioside (12) for biological activity and found them to possess anticomplementary and immunomodulating activity. In view of these activities associated with these molecules we believe future chemical and biological work in this direction would be quite rewarding.

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